

Kholosi Dictionary

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Kholosi is an Indo-Aryan language of Hormozgan, Iran. Many centuries ago, the earliest Kholosi speakers came to Iran from India and settled there in the villages of Kholos and Gotav. They preserved their original language but also melded influences from Persian, Achomi, Balochi, and Gulf Arabic. This dictionary is the first linguistic analysis of Kholosi vocabulary, dedicated to the Kholosi community. I owe my friend Ahmed Etebari the greatest thanks in helping compile this.

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Preface

The data for this lexicon is drawn from various sources. If there is no apparent source label, the word has been recorded in my own fieldwork with Ahmed Etebari [Arora et al., 2021, Arora, 2021]. If the annotation has **A.**, then it is from Anonby and Mohebbi Bahmani [2016] and their unpublished fieldwork data. If there is an annotation **N.**, then it is from Nourzaei [2021]. The entries are formatted in this manner:

word [pronunciation] *part of speech*. meaning. *Etym*: etymology.

If the etymon has a Sanskrit source, then it is given in smallcaps with a reference to its entry number in Turner [1962–1966].

Subentries include compound verbs, idiomatic combinations, and alternative forms. Eventually, I will add example sentences and inflectional paradigms as subentries.

Acknowledgements

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References

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A

- aber** [aber] *n.* cloud. *Etym:* Persian *abr*.
 ▷ **avr** A. [avr] = **aber**
- ačēn** [atʃen] *v.* to come. *Etym:* Sanskrit *ÁTŸĒTI* (227).
- ačānen** [atʃonen] *v.* to blow. *Etym:* unknown.
- akrab** A. [akrab] *n.* scorpion. *Etym:* Achomi *akrab*.
- alʿān** [alʔən] *adv.* now. *Etym:* Persian *alʿān*.
- ambe** [ambe] *n.* mother. *Etym:* Sanskrit *AM-BĀ* (574).
- ambo** [ambo] *n.* mango. *Etym:* Sanskrit *ĀMRĀ* (1268).
 ▷ *ho ambo xāmay* ‘he is eating a mango’
 ▷ *viyāwkā sāf amboyen ke xāvān* ‘the children ate all the mangoes’
- andādo** [andōdo] *n.* darkness. *Etym:* Sanskrit *ANDHĀ* (385).
- ao** [ao] *n.* back (body part). *Etym:* unknown.
- arbāb** A. [arbəb] *n.* chief (tribal). *Etym:* Persian *arbāb* < Arabic.
- assaxān** [assaxən] *n.* bone. *Etym:* Persian *ostoxān*.
- aterā** [aterə] *num.* eight. *Etym:* Sanskrit *AṢṬĀ* (941).
- atto** [atto] *n.* flour. *Etym:* Sanskrit **ĀRTA* (1338).
- attu** [attu] *pron.* you (singular). *Etym:* Sanskrit *TUVĀM* (5889).
 ▷ *attu havālo kiza he?* ‘how are you?’
- avr** A. [avr] = **aber**
- avval** [avval] *adj.* first. *Etym:* Persian *avval*.
- ax** [ax] *n.* eye. *Etym:* Sanskrit *ĀKṢI* (43).

Ā

- āhan** A. [ɔhan] *n.* iron (metal). *Etym:* Persian *āhan*.
- ākebat** [ɔkebat] *adv.* finally. *Etym:* Persian *āqebat*.
- ānen** [ɔnen] *v.* to bring. *Etym:* Sanskrit *Ā-NAYATI* (11714).
- āngul** [ɔŋgul] *n.* finger. *Etym:* Sanskrit *AṄGULA* (134).
 ▷ **ongul** A. [oŋgul] = **āngul**
- āngālen** [ɔŋgolen] *v.* to take off (clothing). *Etym:* unknown.
- āno** [ɔno] *n.* egg. *Etym:* Sanskrit *ĀNDĀ* (1111).
- ārak** [ɔrak] *n.* elbow. *Etym:* Sanskrit *ARAT-NIKA* (603), cf. Sindhi *irika*.

- āse** [ɔse] *pron.* we (1PL). *Etym:* Sanskrit *AS-MAD* (986), cf. Sindhi *asī*.
- āsmān** [ɔsmən] *n.* sky. *Etym:* Persian *āsmān*.
- āvāro** [ɔvoro] *n.* jaw. *Etym:* unknown.
- āve** [ɔve] *pron.* you all (2PL). *Etym:* Sanskrit *YUṢMAD* (10511), cf. Khetrani *avhe*, Lasi *avī*, Sinhala *u^mbə*.

B

- bad** [bad] *conj.* then. *Etym:* Persian *baʿad*.
- bafer** [bafer] *n.* snow, ice. *Etym:* Achomi *bafr*.
- bakkāu** [bakkəu] *n.* frog. *Etym:* perhaps Persian *bak*, Sanskrit *BHĒKA* (9600) or just onomatopoeic.
- balen** [balen] *v.* to run. *Etym:* perhaps Sanskrit *VĀLATI* (11405) ‘to turn, speed towards’ but *v* > *b* is not a Sindhic change.
- bal** [bal] *n.* strength. *Etym:* Sanskrit *BĀLA* (9161).
- balāl** [baləl] *n.* maize, corn. *Etym:* Persian *balāl*.
- barg** [barg] *n.* leaf. *Etym:* Persian *barg*.
- barā** [barə] *num.* two. *Etym:* Sanskrit *DVA* (6648).
- baxoro** [baxoro] *n.* sheep. *Etym:* Sanskrit *BĀRKARA* (9153).
- bāā** [bɔɔ] *n.* father. *Etym:* unknown.
- bābo** [bɔbo] *n.* father’s brother. *Etym:* Sanskrit **BĀBBA* (9209).
- bād** [bɔd] *n.* wind. *Etym:* Persian *bād*.
- bādemjān** [bɔdemdʒən] *n.* eggplant. *Etym:* Persian *bādemjān*.
- bāfen** [bɔfen] *v.* to weave. *Etym:* Persian *bāf-tan*.
- berm** [berm] *n.* eyebrow. *Etym:* Achomi *burm, borm*.
- bexal** [bexal] *n.* arm (incl. upper arm). *Etym:* Persian *bağal*.
- bere** [bere] *adv.* very. *adj.* A. much, many. *Etym:* unusual structure, but probably from a derivative of Sanskrit *BAHÚ* (9187) ‘much, many, great’, cf. Kutchi *baurā* ‘many’ < Sanskrit *BAHURA* (9193).
 ▷ *bere noko* ‘very short’
- bosang** [bosang] *n.* fist. *Etym:* unknown.
- buz** [buz] *n.* mouth, lip. *Etym:* Gulf Arabic *buz*.

Č

- čaben** [tʃaben] *v.* to chew. *Etym:* Sanskrit *CĀRVATI* (4711), cf. Sindhi *caḇaṇu*.

- čango A.** [tʃaŋgo] *adj.* good. *Etym:* Sanskrit CAṄGA (4564).
 ▷ **nečango A.** [netʃaŋgo] *adj.* bad. *Etym:* na ‘not’.
- čarem** [tʃareŋ] *n.* leather. *Etym:* Persian *čarm*.
- čayen** [tʃajen] *v.* to say. *Etym:* Sanskrit *CAVATI (4724), cf. Sindhi *cavaṇu*, Gujarati *cavvū*.
- čarxānen** [tʃarxənen] *v.* to turn. *Etym:* Persian *carxānidan*.
- čāllā** [tʃollə] *num.* four. *Etym:* Sanskrit CATVĀRAḤ (4655), cf. Sindhi *cāri*; assimilation to the numeral suffix *-rā*, probably because *-rr-* is rare and the *r ~ l* alternation is common.
- čel** [tʃel] *n.* waist. *Etym:* cf. Sindhi *celhi*, Dhatki *celh*.
 ▷ **čeli pete A.** [tʃeli pete] *n.* back (body part). *Etym:* *peti* ‘behind’.
- čeman** [tʃeman] *n.* grass. *Etym:* Persian *čaman*.
- čeri** [tʃeri] *n.* chick, baby chicken. *Etym:* Achomi *čori* with umlaut caused by *-i*.
- čoku A.** [tʃoku] *n.* knife. *Etym:* Persian *čāqū* with **ā*-raising.
- čuki** [tʃuki] *n.* chicken. *Etym:* unknown.
- čuri** [tʃuri] *n.* theft. *Etym:* Sanskrit CAURIKĀ (4937).
 ▷ **čuri karen** [tʃuri karen] *v.* to steal. *Etym:* *karen* ‘to do’.

Č^h

- č^hiyen** [tʃ^hijen] *v.* to hit. *Etym:* Sanskrit CHIDATI (5041).
- č^ho** [tʃ^ho] *pron.* what. *Etym:* Sanskrit.
- č^hoy** [tʃ^hoj] *adv.* what. *Etym:* Sanskrit.
- č^hāv** [tʃ^həv] *adv.* why. *Etym:* Sanskrit.

D

- dahri** [dahri] *n.* beard. *Etym:* Sanskrit *DĀMṢṬRA (6250).
 ▷ **dahri tale** [dahri tale] *n.* chin. *Etym:* Lit. ‘under the beard’.
- daliča** [dalitʃa] *n.* window. *Etym:* Persian *dariče*.
- dand** [dand] *n.* tooth. *Etym:* Sanskrit DĀNTA (6152).
 ▷ **dandi genen** [dandi genen] *v.* to bite. *Etym:* *genen* ‘to take, buy’.

- dang** [daŋg] *adj.* full. *Etym:* unknown.
 ▷ **dang t^hiyen** [daŋg t^hijen] *v.* to become full. *Etym:* *t^hiyen* ‘to become’.
- dar** [dar] *n.* door. *Etym:* Persian *dar*.
- daroto** [daroto] *adj.* old (of people). *Etym:* unknown; perhaps from an Iranian cognate to Ossetian *zæronð*, Sanskrit *jāranta* ‘id.’ with *d-*, but so far no apparent leads.
- darpen** [darpen] *v.* to be afraid. *Etym:* Sanskrit DARATI (6190) + MIA *-pp-*.
 ▷ *ho mān tāv derpemay* ‘he is afraid of me’
- dazerā** [dazerə] *num.* ten. *Etym:* Sanskrit DĀŚA (6227).
- dānen** [dānen] *v.* to know. *Etym:* Persian *dānestan*.
- dāno** [dāno] *n.* seed. *Etym:* Persian *dāne*.
- dāzo** [dāzo] *n.* elder brother. *Etym:* Sanskrit *DĀDDA (6261).
- deh¹** [deh] *n.* sun. *Etym:* unknown; note Sanskrit DIVASĀ (6333), but that is already clearly the source of *dizin* ‘day’ and we would not expect *s > h* in Kholosi.
- deh²** [deh] *n.* village. *Etym:* Persian *deh*.
- dem** [dem] *n.* tongue. *Etym:* unknown; related to Zadjali *dīm* ‘tongue’.
- dendel A.** [dendel] *n.* sparrow. *Etym:* unknown.
- derax** [derax] *n.* tree. *Etym:* Persian *deraxt*.
- deres karen** [deres karen] *v.* to cook. *Etym:* probably Persian *dorost kardan*.
- deryāv** [derjəv] *n.* sea. *Etym:* Persian *daryā*.
- derāz** [derəz] *adj.* lying, flat. *Etym:* Persian *darāz*.
 ▷ **derāz kadden** [derəz kadden] *v.* to lie down. *Etym:* *kadden* ‘to pull’; calque of Persian *derāz kašidan*.
- deđā** [deđə] *n.* elder sister. *Etym:* Sanskrit *DIDDĀ (6327).
- dijen** [dijen] *v.* to give. *Etym:* Sanskrit *DINNA (6140).
- dizin** [dizin] *n.* day. *Etym:* Sanskrit DIVASĀ (6333).
- domāx** [doməx] *n.* nose. *Etym:* Persian *damāğ*, Achomi *domāg*.
- dompāč A.** [dompətʃ] *n.* semi-unripe date. *Etym:* unknown; cf. Minabi *dompāzg*.
- doter** [doter] *n.* grandchild. *Etym:* Sanskrit DAÚHITRA (6605).
- dorose** [dorose] *n.* right (direction). *Etym:* Persian *dorost*.
- dud** [dud] *n.* smoke. *Etym:* Persian *dūd*.
- dur** [dur] *adj.* far. *Etym:* Persian *dūr* or Sanskrit DŪRĀ (6495).

E

ekrār [ekrār] *n.* agreement. *Etym:* Persian *eqrār*.

erak karen [erak karen] *v.* to sweat. *Etym:* Persian *araq kardan*.

esal [esal] *n.* honey. *Etym:* Persian *'asal*.

F

feker karen [feker karen] *v.* to think. *Etym:* Persian *fekr kardan*.

fil [fil] *n.* elephant. *Etym:* Persian *fil*.

fitak kadden A. [fitak kadden] *v.* to whistle. *Etym:* cf. Bandari *fike*, Keshmi *fištak* 'whistle' + *kadden* 'to pull'.

fut karen [fut karen] *v.* to breathe. *Etym:* Persian *fūt kardan*.

G

gahro [gahro] *adj.* red. *Etym:* Sanskrit GĀḌHA (4118).

gand [gand] *adj.* dirty. *Etym:* Persian *gande*.

gap [gap] *n.* talk. *Etym:* Persian *gap*.

▷ **gap č^hiyen** [gap tʃ^hijien] *v.* to talk, converse. *Etym:* č^hiyen 'to hit'; calque of Persian *gap zadan*.

gard [gard] *n.* dust. *Etym:* Persian *gard*.

garxen [garxen] *v.* to scratch. *Etym:* unknown.

gavoro [gavoro] *adj.* heavy. *Etym:* Sanskrit GURÚ (4209).

gazzi [gazzi] *n.* rope. *Etym:* unknown.

gāv [gāv] *n.* cow. *Etym:* Persian *gāv* or Sanskrit *GĀVA (4147).

gāy [gāj] *n.* song. *Etym:* *gāyen* 'to sing' + -Ø.

gāyen [gājien] *v.* to sing. *Etym:* Sanskrit GĀYATI (4135).

geh A. N. [geh] *n.* house, room. *Etym:* Sanskrit GĒHĀ (4251).

genen [genen] *v.* to take, buy. *Etym:* Sanskrit GRHṆĀTI (4236).

gere [gere] *n.* unknown. *Etym:* Persian *gereh*.

▷ **gere č^hiyen** [gere tʃ^hijien] *v.* to tie. *Etym:* *gere* + č^hiyen 'to hit'; calque of Persian *gereh zadan*.

gezar [gezar] *n.* carrot. *Etym:* Achomi *gezar*.

geči [geč̣i] *n.* neck. *Etym:* Sanskrit *GICCA (4154).

gohro [gohro] *n.* horse. *Etym:* Sanskrit GHŌṬA (4516).

goj [goḍʒ] *n.* bee. *Etym:* unknown.

gol [gol] *n.* flower. *Etym:* Persian *gul*.

golāndo [golāndo] *adj.* round. *Etym:* Sanskrit GŌLA (4321).

H

hafto [hafto] *n.* week. *Etym:* Persian *hafte*.

hamešā [hamešā] *adv.* always. *Etym:* Persian *hameša*.

hamriš [hamriš] *n.* brother-in-law. *Etym:* Persian *hamriš*.

hat [hat] *n.* hand. *Etym:* Sanskrit HĀSTA (14024).

▷ **hat kadden** [hat kadden] *v.* to give up. *Etym:* *kadden* 'to pull'.

▷ **hate genen** [hate genen] *v.* to hold in the hand. *Etym:* *genen* 'to take, buy'.

havā [havā] *n.* sky. *Etym:* Persian *havā*.

hārro [hārro] *n.* boy. *Etym:* unknown.

he [he] *pron.* he, she, it (proximal); this. *Etym:* cf. Sindhi *hī*.

herri [herri] *n.* girl. *Etym:* unknown.

hesāb karen A. [hesāb karen] *v.* to count. *Etym:* Persian *hesāb* 'counting' + *karen* 'to do'.

heyvān [heyvān] *n.* animal. *Etym:* Persian *heyvān*.

hite [hite] ?

▷ **hite č^hiyen** [hite tʃ^hijien] *v.* to vomit. *Etym:* č^hiyen 'to hit'.

▷ **hite xaten A.** [hite xaten] *v.* to vomit. *Etym:* *xaten* 'to emit'.

hiyo [hijo] *n.* heart. *Etym:* Sanskrit HṚDAYA (14152).

ho [ho] *pron.* he, she, it (distal); that. *Etym:* cf. Sindhi *hū*.

hoko [hoko] *num.* one. *Etym:* Sanskrit ĒKA (2462) with emphatic *h-*, cf. Sindhi *hiku*, Punjabi (*h*)ikk.

hoven [hoven] *pron.* they (distal). *Etym:* *ho*.

hoyen [hojen] *v.* to be. *Etym:* Sanskrit BHĀVATI (9486).

hozen [hozen] *pron.* they (proximal). *Etym:* *ho*.

hulu [hulu] *n.* peach. *Etym:* Persian *hulu*.

J

jakojanvar [ḍʒako ḍʒɔnvar] *n.* animal. *Etym:* Achomi *jakojanvar* < Persian *jānvar* 'animal'.

jar A. [ḍʒar] *n.* war. *Etym:* unknown.

javdān [ḍʒavdan] *n.* table. *Etym:* unknown.

- jādda A.** [d̪ɔ̌ɔdda] *n.* path. *Etym:* Persian *jādde*.
jān [d̪ɔ̌ɔn] *n.* body. *Etym:* Achomi *jān*.
jelak [d̪ɔ̌ɔlak] *n.* clothing, clothes. *Etym:* unknown.
jeng A. [d̪ɔ̌ɔng] *n.* louse. *Etym:* unknown.
jiro [d̪ɔ̌ɔiro] *n.* food. *Etym:* unknown; perhaps related to Sanskrit *JĪRAYATI (5236) ‘to digest’.
jo¹ [d̪ɔ̌ɔ] *post.* of, belonging to; *indicates genitive case.* *Etym:* cf. Sindhi *jo*.
jo² [d̪ɔ̌ɔ] *pron.* who, which; *correlative pronoun.* *Etym:* Sanskrit YÁ (10391).
jo³ [d̪ɔ̌ɔ] *conj.* that; *complementiser.* *Etym:* Sanskrit YÁ (10391).
jodugar [d̪ɔ̌ɔdugar] *n.* witch. *Etym:* Persian *jādugar*.
jodā [d̪ɔ̌ɔdɔ] *adj.* split. *Etym:* Persian *jodā*.
 ▷ **jodā karen** [d̪ɔ̌ɔdɔ karen] *v.* to split. *Etym:* *karen* ‘to do’; calque of Persian *jodā kardan*.
jolo¹ [d̪ɔ̌ɔolo] *n.* front. *Etym:* unknown.
jolo² [d̪ɔ̌ɔolo] *n.* spider. *Etym:* perhaps Sanskrit JĀLA (5213) ‘web’.
juti [d̪ɔ̌ɔuti] *n.* shoe. *Etym:* Achomi *juti* < Gulf Arabic *juti* (pl. *juwāti*) < Hindi *jūtā*.

K

- kabutar** [kabutar] *n.* pigeon. *Etym:* Persian *kabutar*.
kačera A. [kat̪ɔ̌ɔera] *n.* rubbish (piece). *Etym:* Sanskrit KACCARA¹ (2615).
kadden [kadden] *v.* to pull. *Etym:* Sanskrit *KAD̪DHATI (2660).
kak [kak] *n.* flea. *Etym:* Persian *kak*.
kalko [kalko] *n.* cheek. *Etym:* unknown.
kallo [kallo] *n.* head. *Etym:* Persian *kalle*.
kalpak [kalpak] *n.* hat. *Etym:* Turkic *kalpak*.
kalto [kalto] *adj.* big. *Etym:* unknown.
karčax [kart̪ɔ̌ɔax] *n.* knife. *Etym:* Achomi *karčax* < Persian *kard* ‘knife’ + *cāqū* ‘knife’.
 ▷ **karčax č^hiyen** [kart̪ɔ̌ɔax t̪^hijen] *v.* to stab. *Etym:* *č^hiyen* ‘to hit’.
karen [karen] *v.* to do. *Etym:* Sanskrit KARÓTI (2814), cf. Sindhi *karaṇu*.
kassāb [kassɔ̌ɔb] *n.* butcher. *Etym:* Arabic *qassāb*.
kavi [kavi] *adj.* strong. *Etym:* Persian *qavi*.
kāl [kɔ̌ɔl] *adv.* yesterday. *Etym:* Sanskrit KĀLYA (3104).
kāro [kɔ̌ɔro] *adj.* black. *Etym:* Sanskrit KĀLA (3083).
kāti A. [kɔ̌ɔti] *n.* large knife. *Etym:* Sanskrit *KARTA (2853), cf. Gujarati *kāti*.
ke¹ [ke] *post.* to; *accusative–dative case.* *Etym:* Sanskrit KṚTĒ (2184).
ke² [ke] *conj.* that; *complementiser.* *Etym:* Persian *keh*.
kelak [kelak] *n.* son. *Etym:* unknown.
kelam [kelam] *n.* cabbage. *Etym:* Persian *kalam*.
ken [ken] *pron.* who. *Etym:* Sanskrit KAḤ PUNAR (2575).
kend [kend] *n.* knee. *Etym:* unknown; probably Balochi *kóndh* ‘knee’, but note Sanskrit *KHUṆṬA² (3898) ‘corner’ (whence Sindhi *kuṇḍa* ‘corner’, and note historical weakness of short *u* in Kholosi).
kerem [kerem] *n.* worm. *Etym:* Persian *kerm*.
kerā [kerɔ̌ɔ] *pron.* which one. *Etym:* cf. Sindhi *ker*.
kesam [kesam] *n.* vow. *Etym:* Persian *qasam*.
 ▷ **kesam xāyen** [kesam xɔ̌ɔjen] *v.* to vow, swear. *Etym:* *xāyen* ‘to eat’; calque of Persian *kesam xordan*.
kešāvarz [keʃɔ̌ɔvarz] *n.* farmer. *Etym:* Persian *kešāvarz*.
kite [kite] *adv.* where. *Etym:* cf. Sindhi *kithe*.
kizo [kizo] *adv.* how. *Etym:* cf. Hindi *kaise*.
kolen [kolen] *v.* to dig. *Etym:* perhaps Sanskrit *KŌḌḌ (3934).
kolond A. [kolond] *n.* unripe date. *Etym:* unknown.
koloft [koloft] *adj.* thick. *Etym:* Persian *koloft*.
komak [komak] *n.* help. *Etym:* Persian *komak*.
 ▷ **komak karen** [komak karen] *v.* to help. *Etym:* *karen* ‘to do’; calque of Persian *komak kardan*.
konjen [kond̪ɔ̌ɔzen] *v.* to want. *Etym:* Sanskrit KĀN̪KṢATI (3002).
korop A. [korop] *n.* ankle. *Etym:* unknown.
koso [koso] *a.* warm. *Etym:* Sanskrit *KŌṢMA (3552).
kotoro [kotoro] *n.* dog. *Etym:* Sanskrit *KUTTA (3275).
kozoro [kozoro] *n.* man. *Etym:* perhaps Sanskrit GĀRHYA ‘domestic’ > MIA **gajjha*; cf. Domari *kağğā* ‘non-Domari man’, Romani *gažo* ‘non-Romani man’; in any case, the cognates are more likely than the etymon.
 ▷ *deh sonji mā kozoro hu jo nāy-os ali hu* ‘in our village there was a man whose name was Ali’

L

- lakken A.** [lakken] *v.* to suck. *Etym:* unknown, maybe related to *makken* ‘id.’.
- lamer A.** [lamer] *n.* sand. *Etym:* Achomi *lamr*.
- lebās** [lebəs] *n.* clothing. *Etym:* Persian *lebās*.
- lero A.** [lero] *n.* camel. *Etym:* cf. Koroshi Balochi *lera* ‘camel’, exhibiting an instance of marginal retroflexion.
- lojen** [lodʒen] *v.* to rub. *Etym:* unknown.
- lon** [lon] *n.* salt. *Etym:* Sanskrit LAVANĀ (10978).
- loy** [loj] *n.* hair. *Etym:* Sanskrit LÓMAN (11154).
- lāk** [lɔk] *n.* war, fight. *Etym:* unknown.
 ▷ **lāk karen** [lɔk karen] *v.* to fight. *Etym:* *karen* ‘to do’.
- lāren** [lɔren] *v.* to throw. *Etym:* perhaps Sanskrit *RAL (10640).

M

- majbur** [madʒbur] *adj.* compelled. *Etym:* Persian *majbūr*.
 ▷ **majbur karen** [madʒbur karen] *v.* to compel. *Etym:* *karen* ‘to do’.
 ▷ **majbur t^hiyen** [madʒbur t^hijen] *v.* to be compelled. *Etym:* *t^hiyen* ‘to become’.
- makken** [makken] *v.* to suck. *Etym:* Persian *makidan*.
- malum** [malum] *adj.* known. *Etym:* Persian *ma’alum*.
- mangal** [maŋgal] *n.* fire. *Etym:* Sanskrit MAṄGALĀ (9706).
- maren** [maren] *v.* to die. *Etym:* Sanskrit MÁRATĒ (9871).
- marse** [marse] *n.* school. *Etym:* Persian *madrese*.
- matbax** [matbax] *n.* kitchen. *Etym:* Persian *matbax*.
- mate** [mate] *post.* on top of, above, on. *Etym:* Sanskrit MASTA (9926).
 ▷ **mate karen** [mate karen] *v.* to put on (e.g. a robe). *Etym:* *karen* ‘to do’.
- mato** [mato] *n.* head. *Etym:* Sanskrit MASTA (9926).
- matti** [matti] *n.* dirt. *Etym:* Sanskrit MĀRTTIKĀ (10286).
- maxi** [maxi] *n.* fly (insect). *Etym:* Sanskrit MÁKṢIKĀ (9696).
- mač^hi** [mat^hi] *n.* fish. *Etym:* Sanskrit MÁTSYA (9758).
 ▷ **mač^hi kalekant A.** [mat^hi kalekant] *n.* dish, made from a kind of fish and natural red colour from Hormoz Island. *Etym:* unknown.
- mā** [mɔ] *post.* at, in; locative case. *Etym:* Sanskrit MÁDHYA (9804).
- māl** [mɔl] *n.* animal. *Etym:* unknown.
- māren** [mɔren] *v.* to kill. *Etym:* Sanskrit MĀRĀYATI (10066).
- mārez** [mɔrez] *n.* human being; humanity. *Etym:* Perhaps Sanskrit MÁNUṢA (9827) ‘man’, cf. *mers* ‘husband’.
- māv** [mɔv] *n.* mother (affectionate?). *Etym:* Sanskrit MĀTĪ (10016).
- māy** [mɔj] *n.* I (1SG). *Etym:* Sanskrit MA (9691); only northern dialect of Sindhi has similar *mā̃*.
- māz** [mɔz] *n.* meat. *Etym:* Sanskrit MĀMSĀ (9982).
- meda** [meda] *n.* stomach. *Etym:* Persian *me’de*.
- meh** [meh] *n.* rain. *Etym:* Sanskrit MĒGHĀ (10302).
- meo** [meo] *n.* fat (substance). *Etym:* Sanskrit MĒDAS (10323).
- mevo** [mevo] *n.* fruit. *Etym:* Persian *mēva*.
- mers** [mers] *n.* husband. *Etym:* Sanskrit MANUṢYĀ (9828), cf. Sindhi *maṛs*, *murs*; like the Sindhic cognates, shows conflation with PÚRUṢA (8289) ‘man’.
- meter A.** [meter] *n.* urine. *Etym:* Sanskrit MÚTRA (10234).
- meš** [meʃ] *n.* mouse. *Etym:* Persian *mūš*.
- minibus** [minibus] *n.* bus. *Etym:* English *minibus*.
- miri** [miri] *n.* wife. *Etym:* Sanskrit MAHILĀ (9962), cf. Sindhi *mihiri*.
- momo** [momo] *n.* mother’s brother. *Etym:* Sanskrit MĀMA (10055).
- moni** [moni] *n.* bread. *Etym:* Sanskrit MAṆḌĀ (9735), cf. Sindhi *mānī*.
- mosi** [mosi] *n.* mother’s sister. *Etym:* Sanskrit MĀTUḤṢVASŔ (10001).
- mosāfer** [mosɔfer] *n.* traveller. *Etym:* Persian *mosāfer*.
- motor** [motor] *n.* car. *Etym:* English *motor*.
- mov** [mov] *n.* face. *Etym:* Sanskrit MÚKHA (10158).
- movz** [movz] *n.* banana. *Etym:* Persian *movz*.
- mox** [mox] *n.* brain. *Etym:* Persian *mox*.
- moxoro** [moxoro] *n.* ant. *Etym:* Sanskrit MARKAṬA (9883).
- močak** [motʃak] *n.* wrist. *Etym:* Persian *moč* ‘wrist’ + diminutive *-ak*.

N

na [na] *adv.* not (NEG). *Etym:* Sanskrit NÁ (6906).

▷ **ne** [ne] = unstressed form of **na**

nam [nam] *n.* oil. *Etym:* unknown.

nao¹ [nao] *n.* moon. *Etym:* Uncertain; perhaps Sanskrit NÁVA (6983) ‘new’ > ‘new moon’ > ‘moon’.

nao² [nao] *adj.* new. *Etym:* Sanskrit NÁVA (6983).

nari [nari] *n.* throat. *Etym:* Sanskrit NĀDĪ (7047).

nav [nav] *n.* lake. *Etym:* perhaps Sanskrit NĀVĀ (7081) ‘boat’.

naverā [naverā] *num.* nine. *Etym:* Sanskrit NÁVA (6984), cf. Sindhi *nava*.

naxo A. [naxo] *n.* rope. *Etym:* unknown.

nāl A. [nāl] *n.* branch. *Etym:* unknown.

nāno [nāno] *n.* grandfather. *Etym:* Sanskrit *NĀNNA (7059).

nāy [nāj] *n.* name. *Etym:* Sanskrit NĀMAN (7067).

▷ **nāyo** [nājjo] = **nāy**

nefas [nefas] *n.* breath. *Etym:* Persian *nafas*.

negah karen [negah karen] *v.* to hold. *Etym:* Persian *negah kardan*.

nei [nei] *n.* navel. *Etym:* perhaps Sanskrit NĀBHI (7062).

nekter noko A. [nekter noko] *n.* Eid al-Fitr. *Etym:* unknown + *noko* ‘small’.

nekter vazo A. [nekter vazo] *n.* Eid al-Adha. *Etym:* unknown + *vazo* ‘big’.

nemāz A. [neməz] *n.* prayer, namāz. *Etym:* Persian *namāz*.

▷ **nemāz āvel-jo A.** [neməz əvelǰo] *n.* asr prayer. *Etym:* unknown.

▷ **nemāz čāš-jo A.** [neməz tʃəʃǰo] *n.* zuhr prayer. *Etym:* Persian *čāš(t)* ‘lunch’.

▷ **nemāz šām-jo A.** [neməz ʃəmdǰo] *n.* maghrib prayer. *Etym:* Persian *šām* ‘evening’.

▷ **nemāz xāftanj A.** [neməz xəftəndǰ] *n.* isha prayer. *Etym:* Persian *xoftan* ‘to sleep’.

▷ **vazile** [vazile] see **vazile**

nevalm [nevalm] *adj.* bad. *Etym:* Achomi *ne* + *valm*.

▷ **nevaletm** [nevaletm] = **nevalm**

▷ **nevaletmte** [nevaletmte] = **nevalm**

neč [neč] *n.* fingernail. *Etym:* Achomi *neč*.

nim [nim] *adj.* half. *Etym:* Persian *nīm*.

nimur [nimur] *n.* lemon. *Etym:* Achomi *nimur*.

nivisen [nivisen] *v.* to write. *Etym:* Persian *naveštan*, *neveštan*.

noko [noko] *adj.* small; short. *Etym:* Sanskrit NIKTĀ (7150), cf. Punjabi *nikkā*.

noni [noni] *n.* grandmother. *Etym:* Sanskrit *NĀNNA (7059).

nurati [nurati] *n.* fog. *Etym:* unknown.

O

olu¹ [olu] *n.* potato. *Etym:* Sanskrit ĀLU (1388), cf. Sindhi *ālū*.

olu² [olu] *n.* plum. *Etym:* Persian *ālu*.

ongul A. [oŋgul] = **āngul**

P

pal A. [pal] *n.* feather. *Etym:* dialectal form of Persian *par*.

▷ **pal karen A.** [pal karen] *v.* to fly. *Etym:* *karen* ‘to do’.

panjerā [pandǰerā] *num.* five. *Etym:* Sanskrit PĀNCA (7655), cf. Sindhi *panja*.

paren [paren] *v.* to read, study; to sing. *Etym:* Sanskrit PĀTHATI (7712).

parono [parono] *adj.* old (of things). *Etym:* Sanskrit PURĀṆĀ (8283).

▷ **perāno** [perəno] = **parono**

parvāna [parvəna] *n.* butterfly. *Etym:* Persian *parvāne*.

parvāz karen [parvəz karen] *v.* to fly. *Etym:* Persian *parvāz kardan*.

pas [pas] *conj.* so. *Etym:* Persian *pas*.

pay [paj] *n.* foot. *Etym:* Sanskrit PADĀ (7747).

▷ **pay karen** [paj karen] *v.* to put on the feet, e.g. socks, shoes. *Etym:* *karen* ‘to do’.

pačen [patʃen] *v.* to come. *Etym:* Sanskrit PRĀBHŪTA (8716), cf. Sindhi *pahucaṇu* ‘to reach’.

pašem [paʃem] *n.* wool. *Etym:* Persian *pašam*.

pālā diyen [pələ dijen] *v.* to insult. *Etym:* unknown.

pān [pən] *pron.* self (REFL). *Etym:* Sanskrit TMĀN (5983) ‘self’, cf. Sindhi *pāna*.

pātil A. [pətɪl] *n.* pot. *Etym:* Sanskrit PĀTRA (8055), cf. Hindi *patilā*.

pātlun [pətlun] *n.* pants. *Etym:* English *pan-taloon*.

pāyo [pəjo] *n.* leg. *Etym:* Sanskrit PĀDA (8056).

penden [penden] *v.* to see. *Etym:* unknown.

▷ *kunju hiki šahr vazi ke pendeya?* ‘do you want to see a big city?’

perāno [perəno] = **parono**

pet [pet] *n.* belly, abdomen. *Etym:* Sanskrit *PĒṬṬA (8376).

petak [petak] *n.* leaf. *Etym:* unknown; perhaps Sanskrit PĀTTRA (7733) ‘leaf’, unlikely that IA *-aka* was retained but there is also productive Iranian *-ak* in Kholosi (cf. *močāk* ‘fist’).

peter [peter] *n.* boy. *Etym:* Sanskrit PUTRĀ (8265).

peti [peti] *post.* behind. *Etym:* Sanskrit PRṢṬHĀ (8371) ‘back’.

peč [pet̪] = **p^heč**

pečānen [pet̪ənən] *v.* to wrap. *Etym:* Persian *pēčīdan*.

pejal [peǰal] *n.* bedroom. *Etym:* unknown.

peššāren [peš̪ʁən] *v.* to push. *Etym:* Persian *fešār*.

piči **A.** [pīʃi] *adj.* little (an amount). *Etym:* unknown.

piko [piko] *n.* horn. *Etym:* unknown.

piyen [pijen] *v.* to drink. *Etym:* Sanskrit PĪBATI (8209).

piško [piško] *n.* forehead. *Etym:* perhaps Persian *pēš*.

poni [poni] *v.* water. *Etym:* Sanskrit PĀNĪYA (8082).

▷ **poni mate p^hiyen** [poni mate p^hijen] *v.* to float. *Etym:* *mate* ‘on’ + *p^hiyen* ‘to stand’.

portaxāl [portaxəl] *n.* orange (fruit). *Etym:* Persian *portegāl* < Portuguese *Portugal*.

pov [pov] *n.* younger brother. *Etym:* probably Sanskrit PŌTA (8399) ‘young of animal or plant’.

pu [pu] *n.* father. *Etym:* Sanskrit PITṚ (8179), cf. Sindhi *pū*.

▷ **p^hu** **A.** [p^hu] = **pu**

puni jelji [puni ǰeldǰi] *n.* cotton. *Etym:* first element from Sanskrit *PŪNA (8326) ‘bundle or roll of cotton’, cf. Sindhi *pūñi*.

pyāj [pjəǰ] *n.* onion. *Etym:* Persian *piyāz* but *z > j* is unusual.

P^h

p^heč [p^het̪] *n.* tail. *Etym:* Sanskrit PICCHA (8151).

▷ **peč** [pet̪] = **p^heč**

p^hen [p^hen] *n.* younger sister. *Etym:* **b^hen* < Sanskrit BHAGINĪ (9349), cf. Sindhi *bhiṇu*, *bhiṇa*.

▷ **pen** [pen] = **p^hen**

p^hepi [p^hepi] *n.* father’s sister. *Etym:* Sanskrit *PHUPPHU (9089) with gender unlaut in the first vowel.

p^hi [p^hi] *n.* earth. *Etym:* **b^hui* < Sanskrit BHŪMI (9557).

p^hiyen [p^hijen] *v.* to stand. *Etym:* **b^hiyen* < Sanskrit ŪRDHVĀ (2426) ‘standing, erect’, cf. Sindhi *ubihāṇu*, *bihāṇu* ‘to stand’.

p^hu **A.** [p^hu] = **pu**

R

rat [rat] *n.* blood. *Etym:* Sanskrit RAKTA (10539).

-rā [rə] *suf.* numeral suffix. *Etym:* cf. Kutchi *hekiro* ‘one’ with suffix *-ro*, but note that Kholosi adds this suffix to every number except ‘one’.

rāsta [rəstə] *adj.* straight. *Etym:* Persian *rāsta*.

rāt [rət] *n.* night. *Etym:* Sanskrit RĀTRĪ (10702).

rayen [rajen] *v.* to play. *Etym:* Sanskrit RĀMATĒ (10628).

remiz **A.** [remiz] *n.* termite. *Etym:* unknown; cf. Minabi *ramiz*.

rišo **A.** [riʃo] *n.* root. *Etym:* Persian *riše*.

rotub **A.** [rotub] *n.* date (fruit). *Etym:* Persian *rotāb*.

rovšan [rovʃan] *adj.* bright. *Etym:* Persian *rowšan*.

roxo [roxo] *n.* stone. *Etym:* unknown.

royen [rojen] *v.* to cry. *Etym:* Sanskrit RŌDATI (10840).

rubā [rubə] *n.* fox. *Etym:* Persian *rūbah*.

ruh [ruh] *n.* soul. *Etym:* Persian *rūh*.

S

sabā [sabə] *adv.* tomorrow. *Etym:* Achomi; cf. Luri *sabo*.

sagen [sagen] *v.* to be able to, can. *Etym:* Sanskrit SAGHNŌTI (13080), cf. Sindhi *sagaṇu*.

sago **A.** [sago] *n.* rope. *Etym:* unknown.

sanā [sanə] *adj.* tired. *Etym:* perhaps from the set Sanskrit *ŚAṬṬA ~ ŚAṬHA ~ ŚAṆṬHĀ ~ *ŚAṆṬHARA ~ ŚAṆḌHĀ (12270) ‘defective’ or Sanskrit ŚLAKṢṆĀ (12372) (whence *sino* ‘thin’).

saodo [saodo] *n.* rabbit. *Etym:* perhaps Sanskrit ŚAŚĀ (12357) ‘hare’ (cf. Sindhi *saha*, *sahyaṛo*), but we would usually expect Kholosi **saz(o)* from that.

sap [sap] *n.* snake. *Etym:* Sanskrit SARPĀ (13271), cf. Sindhi *sapu*.

sarbāz [sarbɔz] *n.* soldier. *Etym:* Persian *sar-bāz*.

saterā [saterɔ] *num.* seven. *Etym:* Sanskrit SAPTĀ (13139), cf. Sindhi *sata*.

sau [sau] *num.* one hundred. *Etym:* Sanskrit ŚATĀ (12278).

sāf [sɔf] *det.* all. *Etym:* Sanskrit SĀRVA (13276).

sākko A. [sɔkko] *adj.* dry. *Etym:* Sanskrit ŚUṢKA (12548), cf. Sindhi *suko*; note that short vowels like *u* are unstable.

sāl¹ [sɔl] *n.* year. *Etym:* Persian *sāl*.

sāl² [sɔl] *n.* rice. *Etym:* probably Sanskrit ŚĀLI (12415).

sāhel [sɔhel] *n.* beach. *Etym:* Persian *sāhel*.

sānda [sɔnda] *post.* with, *comitative case.* *Etym:* Sanskrit SANTAKA (13127), cf. Sindhi *sando*, Marwari *hando*.
▷ *hinki sānda* ‘together’

sāo [sɔo] *adj.* green. *Etym:* Sanskrit ŚYĀVĀ (12672).
▷ *sāvāyi* [sɔvɔji] *n.* grass. *Etym:* -āyi ‘?’.

sāro A. [sɔro] *n.* plain (geographical feature). *Etym:* perhaps Persian *sahrā*.

sāxtemān [sɔxtemɔn] *n.* building. *Etym:* Persian *sāxtemān*.

semen [semen] *v.* to sleep. *Etym:* Sanskrit SVAPNĀYATĒ (13905), cf. Sindhi *sumhaṇu*.

senen [senen] *v.* to hear. *Etym:* Sanskrit ŚRṆŌTI (12598), cf. Sindhi *suṇaṇu*.

sere [sere] *n.* village. *Etym:* Persian *sere*.

siben [siben] *v.* to sew. *Etym:* Sanskrit ŚIVYATI (13444), cf. Sindhi *sibaṇu*.

sino¹ [sino] *adj.* thin. *Etym:* Sanskrit ŚLAKṢNĀ (12372), cf. Sindhi *sanho*.

sino² [sino] *n.* chest. *Etym:* Persian *sine*.

sir [sir] *n.* garlic. *Etym:* Persian *sir*.

siḍa [siḍa] *adj.* straight. *Etym:* Sanskrit SIDHA (13401).
▷ **siza** [siza] = **siḍa**

sohbat karen [sohbat karen] *v.* to talk, converse. *Etym:* Persian *sohbat kardan*.

sokolo [sokolo] *adj.* white. *Etym:* Sanskrit ŚUKRĀ (12506).

sokoro [sokoro] *adj.* each. *Etym:* unknown.

sorāx genen A. [sorɔx genen] *v.* to ask. *Etym:* Persian *sorāḡ* + *genen* ‘to take’, interesting as Indo-Aryan equivalents for ‘to ask’ also have a similar syntax as ‘to take’.

suk karen A. [suk karen] *v.* to pain, ache. *Etym:* unknown, cf. Sindhi *hūka* ‘pain, alarm’ < Sanskrit *HŪKKĀ (14144) but initial *s* > *h* is not there in Sindhic.

surov A. [surov] *n.* kind of dish. *Etym:* unknown.

sut kadden A. [sut kadden] *v.* to whistle. *Etym:* Persian *sūt* + Kholosi *kadden* ‘to pull’.

Š

šal A. [ʃal] *n.* sun. *Etym:* unknown.

šam [ʃam] *n.* candle. *Etym:* Persian *šam*’.

šadi [ʃɔdi] *n.* monkey. *Etym:* Achomi *šādī*.

šajjo [ʃɔdʒdʒo] *adj.* clean. *Etym:* perhaps Sanskrit ŚŌDHYA (12632) ‘to be cleaned’ but uncertain if *š* ever retained in Kholosi.
▷ **šajjo karen** [ʃɔdʒdʒo karen] *v.* to wipe. *Etym:* *karen* ‘to do’.

šano [ʃɔno] *n.* shoulder. *Etym:* Persian *šāne*.

šār [ʃɔr] *n.* ash. *Etym:* *č^hār < Sanskrit KṢĀRĀ (3674).

šekār karen [ʃekɔr karen] *v.* to hunt. *Etym:* Persian *šekār kardan*.

šekken [ʃekken] *v.* to sneeze. *Etym:* *č^hikkan < Sanskrit CHIKKĀ (5032).

šerā [ʃerɔ] *num.* six. *Etym:* *č^ha < Sanskrit ṢAṢ (12803).

šir [ʃir] *n.* milk. *Etym:* Persian *šir*.

šnāv karen [ʃnɔv karen] *v.* to swim. *Etym:* Persian *šenā kardan*.

šomār [ʃomɔr] *n.* north. *Etym:* Persian *šomāl*.

šomār karen [ʃomɔr karen] *v.* to count. *Etym:* Persian *šomār kardan*.

šomāren [ʃomɔren] *v.* to count. *Etym:* Persian *šomāridan*.

šowko A. [ʃowko] *n.* falcon. *Etym:* unknown; cf. Minabi *šowmak*.

šorko [ʃorko] *n.* boy. *Etym:* *č^hokro < Sanskrit *CHŌKARA (5070).

šurki [ʃurki] *n.* girl. *Etym:* *č^hokri < Sanskrit *CHŌKARA (5070).

šuš [ʃuʃ] *n.* sewing needle. *Etym:* unknown; perhaps Sanskrit SŪCĪ (13551) ‘needle’ with sibilant harmony, but no parallels to this change.

T

tamāta [tamɔta] *n.* tomato. *Etym:* English *tomato*.

tale [tale] *post.* beneath, below, under. *Etym:* Sanskrit TALA (5731).

tap [tap] *n.* goat. *Etym:* unknown.

tarix [tarix] *adj.* angry. *Etym:* Persian *tarīx*.

taxte A. [taxte] *n.* bed. *Etym:* Persian *taxt*.

tazen [tazen] *v.* to tie. *Etym:* unknown.

- te** [te] *post.* to, *allative case*; through, using, *instrumental case*. *Etym:* Sanskrit.
- teng karen** [teŋg karen] *v.* to swell. *Etym:* unknown.
- tereṛā** [tereṛɑ] *num.* three. *Etym:* Sanskrit TRÁYAḤ (5994), cf. Sindhi *ṭ(r)e*.
- tergi A.** [tergi] *n.* prayer, namāz (*only used by old men*). *Etym:* unknown.
- ters karen A.** [ters karen] *v.* to fear. *Etym:* Persian *tars* ‘fear’ + *karen* ‘to do’.
- to anen** [to anen] *v.* to vomit. *Etym:* unknown.
- tof** [tof] *n.* spit. *Etym:* Persian *tof*.
- ▷ **tof karen** [tof karen] *v.* to spit. *Etym:* *karen* ‘to do’.
- ▷ **tof lären A.** [tof lören] *v.* to spit. *Etym:* probably *lären* ‘to throw’.
- too** [too] *post.* above. *Etym:* Sanskrit, cf. Punjabi *te*.
- tula** [tula] *n.* puppy. *Etym:* Persian *tūla*.
- tum A.** [tum] *n.* palm (tree). *Etym:* unknown; cf. Minabi *tuhm*.
- tur kadden** [tur kadden] *v.* to lie down. *Etym:* unknown.
- tābesān** [tɑbesɑn] *n.* summer. *Etym:* Persian *tābestān*.
- tāffo** [tɑffo] *n.* apple. *Etym:* Gulf Arabic *tuffāḥ*.
- tāro** [tɑro] *n.* star (celestial body). *Etym:* Sanskrit TĀRĀ (5798).
- tāv** [tɑv] *n.* from, *ablative case*. *Etym:* Sanskrit.
- ▷ *ho mān tāv derpemay* ‘he is afraid of me’
- ▷ *ho mān tāv tarix he* ‘he is angry at me’
- ▷ *ho sāhel tāv belemay* ‘he runs away from the beach’

T^h

- t^hal** [t^hal] *n.* mountain. *Etym:* Sanskrit STHĀLA (13774) ‘dry land’.
- t^hallo** [t^hallo] *adj.* fat. *Etym:* Sanskrit STHŪLĀ (13776), cf. Sindhi *thulho*.
- t^hādo** [t^hɑdo] *adj.* cold. *Etym:* Sanskrit STABDHA (13676), cf. Sindhi *thadho*.
- t^hārgo** [t^hɑrgo] *adj.* tall, long. *Etym:* Sanskrit DĪRGHĀ (6386), cf. Sindhi *ḍ(r)igho*.
- t^hiv** [t^hiv] *n.* girl. *Etym:* Sanskrit DUHITṚ (6481) ‘daughter’, cf. Sindhi *dhiu*.
- t^hiyen** [t^hijen] *v.* to become. *Etym:* Sanskrit *STHĀTI (13752).
- t^hoyen** [t^hojen] *v.* to wash. *Etym:* Sanskrit *DHAUVATI (6886).
- ▷ **lāšo t^hoyen A.** [lɑʃo t^hojen] *v.* to bathe. *Etym:* unknown.

U

- utubus** [utubus] *n.* bus. *Etym:* English *auto-bus*.

V

- vadden** [vadden] *v.* to cut. *Etym:* Sanskrit VARDHAYATI (11381), cf. Sindhi *vaḍḥaṇu*.
- ▷ *ho ambo ke karčax te vaddayi* ‘he cut the mango with a knife’
- valm** [valm] *adj.* good. *n.* right (direction). *Etym:* Achomi *valm*.
- ▷ **valem** [valem] = **valm**
- ▷ **valemte** [valemte] = **valm**
- vanen** [vanen] *v.* to go. *Etym:* Sanskrit VYĒTI (12223).
- var** [var] *adj.* greater. *Etym:* Sanskrit VĀRA (11308).
- varet** [varet] *n.* groom, son-in-law. *Etym:* perhaps Sanskrit VARĀ (11309).
- vaxte** [vaxte] *adv.* when. *Etym:* Persian *vaxte*.
- vaz** [vaz] *n.* bride. *Etym:* Sanskrit VADHŪ (11250).
- vazile** [vazile] *adv.* in the morning. *n.* **A.** fajr prayer. *Etym:* unknown; cf. Sindhi *vaḍo velo* ‘early morning’, Arabic *faḍīla* ‘virtue’.
- vazo** [vazo] *adj.* big, large. *Etym:* Sanskrit VADRA (11225).
- ▷ **vazoro A.** [vazoro] *n.* elder, chief. *Etym:* *-ro* person suffix (?), cf. *kozoro*.
- vālo** [vɑlo] *post.* below. *Etym:* unknown.
- vāt¹** [vɑt] *n.* mouth. *Etym:* Sanskrit VYĀTTA (12196).
- vāt²** [vɑt] *n.* path, road. *Etym:* Sanskrit VĀRTMAN (11366).
- ▷ **vāt vanen** [vɑt vanen] *v.* to walk. *Etym:* *vanen* ‘to go’.
- vāv** [vɑv] *n.* wind. *Etym:* Sanskrit VĀYŪ (11544).
- ▷ **vāv č^hiyen** [vɑv t^hijen] *v.* to swell. *Etym:* *č^hiyen* ‘to hit’.
- velāt A.** [velɑt] *n.* village. *Etym:* unknown.
- velkaj** [velkaj] *n.* left (direction). *Etym:* unknown.
- veten A. N.** [veten] *v.* to say. *Etym:* unknown, perhaps Sanskrit VĀRTTA (11564) ‘talk, tidings’.
- vezen** [vezen] *v.* to sit. *Etym:* Sanskrit ŪPAVIŚATI (2245), cf. Sindhi *vehanu*.
- viyāv** [vijɑv] *n.* child. *Etym:* unknown; perhaps from Sanskrit VIVĀHĀ (11920) ‘marriage’ or Sanskrit VIVĀHIN (11925) ‘through marriage’.

- ▷ Plural: *viyāvkā*
- ▷ **viyāv vānen** [vijəv vānen] *v.* to give birth. *Etym:* unknown.
- ▷ **vyāvāy** [vjavāy] *n.* family. *Etym:* -āy ‘?’.
- vizerā** [vizerə] *num.* twenty. *Etym:* Sanskrit VIMŚATÍ (11616), cf. Sindhi *vīhe*.
- vov vov karen A.** [vov vov karen] *v.* to bark (of a dog). *Etym:* cf. Hindi *bhō*, Sindhi *bhī* + *karen* ‘to do’.
- vozo** [vozo] *adj.* near. *Etym:* cf. Sindhi *vejhō*.

X

- xal** [xal] *n.* skin, bark (of a tree). *Etym:* Sanskrit KHALLA (3848), cf. Sindhi *khala*.
- xallo** [xallo] *n.* barley. *Etym:* unknown.
- xarāb** [xarəb] *adj.* rotten. *Etym:* Persian *xarāb*.
- xars** [xars] *n.* tears. *Etym:* Achomi *xars*.
- xaru** [xaru] *n.* date (fruit). *Etym:* Persian *xormā*.
- xaten** [xaten] *v.* to shine. *Etym:* unknown.
- xān A.** [xən] *n.* smell. *Etym:* unknown.
 - ▷ **xān diyen** [xən diyen] *v.* to smell bad. *Etym:* *diyen* ‘to give’.
 - ▷ **xān xaten A.** [xən xaten] *v.* to smell (a scent). *Etym:* *xaten* ‘?’.
- xārja** [xərdʒa] *prep.* outside. *Etym:* Persian *xārej*.
- xāti** [xəti] *n.* stick, wood. *Etym:* Sanskrit KĀṢṬHĀ (3120), cf. Sindhi *kāth*.
- xāyen** [xəjen] *v.* to eat. *Etym:* Sanskrit *KHĀ-DATI (3865), cf. Sindhi *khāñu*.
- xāz A.** [xəz] *n.* grass. *Etym:* Sanskrit GHĀSĀ (4471), cf. Sindhi *ghāhu*.
- xāzen A.** [xəzen] *v.* to cough. *Etym:* Sanskrit KĀSĀ (3138) with onomatopoeic *kh-* just like cognates; note that none of the

s > h languages retain this word, Sindhi has *kharighi*.

- xelen** [xelen] *v.* to laugh. *Etym:* Sanskrit *KHID (3882).
- xeren** [xeren] *v.* to fall. *Etym:* perhaps Sanskrit KṢĀRATI (3663).
- xers** [xers] *n.* bear. *Etym:* Persian *xers*.
- kez karen A.** [kez karen] *v.* to run. *Etym:* unknown.
- xob** [xob] *adj.* good. *Etym:* Persian *xūb*.
- xoli** [xoli] *adj.* empty. *Etym:* Persian *xālī*.
- xomen** [xomen] *v.* to burn. *Etym:* perhaps Sanskrit *KṢĀṆA (3665).
- xorāk** [xorək] *n.* food. *Etym:* Persian *xorāk*.
- xorg A.** [xorg] *n.* embers. *Etym:* unknown.
- xorši** [xoʃi] *n.* sun. *Etym:* Achomi, cf. Persian *x(w)oršid*.
- xuk** [xuk] *n.* pig. *Etym:* Persian *xūk*.

Z

- zardo** [zardo] *adj.* yellow. *Etym:* Persian *zarde*.
- zayfā** [zajfə] *n.* woman. *Etym:* Arabic *za‘ifa* ‘weak woman’, cf. Brahui *zaifa* ‘wife’.
- zemesān** [zemesən] *n.* winter. *Etym:* Persian *zemestān*.
- zenavās** [zenavəs] *adj.* hungry (*uncertain lemmatisation*). *Etym:* unknown.
 - ▷ *zenao ni* ‘I am not hungry’
- zendegi karen** [zendegi karen] *v.* to live. *Etym:* Persian *zendagi kardan*.
 - ▷ *āse hamešā he deh mā zendegi kār* ‘we have always lived in this village’
- zereng** [zereŋg] *adj.* clever. *Etym:* Persian *zereng*.
- zin A.** [zin] *n.* saddle. *Etym:* Persian *zīn*.
- zorat** [zorat] *n.* corn, maize. *Etym:* Persian *zorat*.